
Communist Manifesto: A Marxist View on the Class-Based Society

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ABSTRACT

"Workers of the world, unite!" - Karl Marx

The famous quote given in the Communist manifesto was a call for the workers from all over the world, to unite and stand up against the capitalist society. "Communism" a word derived from Latin word "Communis", which means shared or common. During the period of 16th to 18th century, a wave of Industrialization has expanded in England, which gave birth to the capitalist class. The emergence of capitalist class in the society has propagated an idea of wealth accumulation and distributing it in producing things which should have economic value. This class entirely believed in wealth generation rather in welfare generation. This propagation has led to economic inequality and a ghetto like situation. Karl Heinrich Marx, a German sociologist, historian and an economist of that time condemned this wealth accumulating society and highlighted the injustice and the inequalities that were faced by the particular section of the society creating a social unrest among them. Marx was a famous critique of capitalism and supported the dictatorship of Proletariats (Workers). He along with Fredrich Engels wrote this communist manifesto and vocalized the class struggle that emerged after the Industrialization. Overall, this research article has been written to accentuate the significant societal changes that took place after the Industrialization in England and the class struggle and public outrage that supported Marx in building a theoretical manifesto named as "Communist Manifesto", highlighting the urgency of a global movement to dismiss the class

differentiation. The data will be collected from the secondary sources such as relevant books, historical magazines and articles. The expansion and the workers unrest will be shown with the help of Maps. The research methods will be historical and explanatory.

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Introduction:

During the period between 16th to 18th century, Industrialization was taking place in entire England. This continuous development has created a differentiation amongst the classes: the bourgeoisie or the capitalist class and the proletariat or the worker class. With due course of time, an ambience of class domination was created where the capitalist class were the privileged and the workers or the Proletariats were being deprived of their basic necessities. They were bound to work under less than minimum necessary wages; the economy was going through extreme disequilibrium, the wealth accumulation was primary concept rather than Welfare. This suppression of worker class created a social agitation and ignited the proletariat class to unite together and stand up against the injustices they were facing. Karl H. Marx, a prominent German sociologist and economist criticized this societal behavior of the capitalist and decided to launch a manifesto later named as “Communist Manifesto” to present the ideas of workers unity, bourgeoisie injustices and the significance on the word “Common”. The primary objective of this article is to bring out the ideas of Karl Marx that were propounded through the communist manifesto and the reason behind framing it and also the role of Karl Marx as a father of “Communism”.

What is meaning of Communism?

It is basically a political and economic ideology that promotes a classless and stateless society under which the means of production such as factories, farms and resources are collectively owned by the community instead of any particular individual or corporation.

The goal of Communism:

The basic goal of this ideology is to create an ambience where there is not an iota of social misbalance and there is an economic equality amongst different sections of the society.

Who was Karl Marx?

Karl Heinrich Marx was a revolutionary sociologist, historian and economist. He was born in 1818 in Prussia, Germany. From 1830-1835, he completed his high school in Trier and went onto to achieve a doctorate degree from university of Jena, in the year 1841. During his formative years and adulthood, he experienced a social misbalance and extreme dominance of the capitalist class. He had a critical ideology towards the social situation that was going in the Europe after the period of Industrialization. To vocalise his ideas and political thoughts he decides to write a manifesto where he propounded the ideology of “Communism”.

The core principles of Communism:

- Common Ownership:

This means that the major resources such as industries and means of production are no longer under the control of an individual instead these resources are collectively owned by the communities.

- A Classless Society:

The basic agenda of communism is to remove the class distinction and ensure equality on every ground.

- Distributions on the basis on needs of the people:

According to this principle, the goods and services are supposed to be distributed amongst public on the basis of their requirements rather the amount of wealth they are owing.

- Abolishing of State:

Communism was completely against the state governing society rather it wants the self- regulating society.

Agenda of Communist Manifesto:

Karl Marx along with another revolutionary German sociologist and philosopher Fredrich Engels proposed this manifesto in the year 1848. This communist manifesto highlights the working conditions of the workers and the necessity of the unification of the workers and their rebel against the capitalist class. It is basically a seminal political pamphlet that articulated the significant objectives and theory of communism. It accentuates the details about a materialistic historical development which emphasizes on the class struggles which led to the exploitation of the Proletariat class by the bourgeoisie class. Marx

and Engels have supported the proletariat revolution and wanted to establish a classless and stateless society where the means of resources are supposed to be collectively shared amongst the community.

Impact of Communism:

Communism had a powerful impact on the global history. It was adapted due to various reasons. The political reason could be seen from multiple examples like the centralized control and authoritarian rule in the Soviet Union under Stalin and China under Mao Zedong or the Cold War dynamics. The economic reason can be seen from the inefficiencies and shortages in the distribution of goods and services amongst communities and the social reasons could be seen from the suppression of freedom of speech, rights, etc. Communism inspired many revolutions and political shifts.

Literature Review:

- 2025, Britanica, the authors have talked about the public ownership and the equal distribution of the resources and services amongst general public.
- 2024, Well- Klinton, the author has highlighted the books, theories written by the Karl Marx based on the communism and their impact on the political economy.
- 2003, Stanford, this article has vocalised the thoughts of Karl Marx regarding his ideology on the proletariat's situation and the dominance they faced by the capitalist class.
- 2015, Unacademy, this article talks about the early life of Karl Marx, what has inspired him to draw out the theories and the famous works written by him. The author has also highlighted the Marx's views on Economic and the Social System.
- 2024, Nicki Cole, under this article the author has summarised the main aspects of the communist manifesto and the basic agenda that influenced its writings.
- 2020, Marcello Musto, this article talks about the role of Fredrich Engels in preparing the communist ideology and supporting Karl Marx in building the communist manifesto.

Research Scope:

This Research will talk about the theories and ideologies that inspired Karl Marx and Fredrich Engels in preparing the communist manifesto which outlines the situation of the Proletariat and the dominance they faced from the capitalist class. Communist Manifesto out sketch the need for the unification of the Proletariat class against the bourgeoisie class and creating a classless society.

• Communist Manifesto cover page from the Google Images

Research Methodology:

The Research will be based on the descriptive and explanatory types of research methods. The previous literary works are explained under the literature review section. The data will be collected from the secondary sources such as historical articles, books and notes. The accuracy of the data will be dependent on the Maps and pictorial representation of the relevant information collected from various sources. The research scope for the study would explain the importance of the selected topic. The researcher has tried not to breach any ethical or moral standards in the process of data collection. Every represented Map will be explained briefly. Finally, a well-explained conclusion will be given to focus on the prominent aspects of the research article.

Data Analysis:

The communism affect will be shown with the help of a Maps taken from the relevant sources which shows the expansion of the ideas of the Karl Marx and Fredrich Engels into various societies of the world.

Map Analysis:

The eastern bloc countries known as Communist bloc including Soviet Union, Eastern Germany, Poland, Czechoslovakia, Hungary and Romania, Bulgaria, Albania and Yugoslavia, have adapted this ideology and aligned with the Soviet Union during the cold war, roughly from 1945-1990. These

countries political state was relying upon the ideology of sharing or common and no individual preference.

Map 1: The Eastern Bloc Countries under Communism taken from the Google images

10 Point Plan Communist Manifesto

1	Abolition of Private Property No longer have private ownership of property.
2	Heavy Progressive or Graduated income Tax Take more money from people who have higher income.
3	Abolish Right of Inheritance State acquires citizen's property upon their death. Families no longer get heirlooms and inheritance.
4	Confiscate Property Owned by Emigrants and Rebels These citizens no longer have rights to their property.
5	Establish National Bank All money and loans are owned by the federal government which constitutes a monopoly.
6	Nationally Controlled Communications and Transport State controls all communication and travel.
7	Government Ownership of the Means of Production Factories, land, and natural resources.
8	Industrial and Agricultural Armies Everyone is liable to work.
9	Redistribute Population Eliminate sovereignty of state and town by redistributing people.
10	Free and Public Education Elimination of children doing factory work and combine education and manufacturing.

The key principle of Communist Manifesto taken from the Google Images.

Communist Manifesto:

Communist Manifesto is structured under 4 sections:

- 1) The class struggle between the bourgeoisie and the proletariat class
- 2) The connections between the proletariat and the communist class
- 3) The interrelations between the socialist and the communist literature
- 4) The relation of the communist in relation to other parties

Conclusion:

This research article has been written to vocalize the political and economic thoughts and ideas of the revolutionary economist and a sociologist Karl Marx. Marx was a German, sociologist who had experienced a class differentiation during his life span. Due to his rebellious and revolutionary attitude, he was debarred from acquiring a job in the university and had to face biasness on several grounds. These kinds of sociological class – based differentiation has encouraged him to frame his political idea of a class-less society and he propounded the theory of Communism. “Communism”, basically means to share the resources and the services collectively amongst the community instead of an individual. After the period of industrialization, the world has seen a class-difference amongst proletariat or the workers class and the bourgeoisie class or the capitalist class. Workers were going through extreme dominance of the capitalist class and they were not given the basic amenities on the equal basis. This situation caused a dire need of the workers to get united against the capitalist classes’ injustices and Marx along with another German revolutionary prepared a manifesto to support the theory of communism. This manifesto outlines the necessity of creating a classless and stateless society. Overall, this research article has tried to bring out the basic principles of Marx’s manifesto and how it affected the world.

References:

- *Blackshirts and Reds*, Michael Parenti, (n.d.).
- The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica. (2025, April 24). *The Communist Manifesto | Summary*,
- *quotations, & facts*. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/The-Communist-Manifesto>
- Communist and post-communist studies. (n.d.). www.jstor.org.
- <https://www.jstor.org/journal/commandpostcomm>
- *Subject: Communism | Journal of Democracy*. (n.d.). Journal of Democracy.
- <https://www.journalofdemocracy.org/subjects/communism/>
- McLellan, T, D., Feuer, & S, L. (2025, May 9). *Karl Marx | Books, Theory, Beliefs, Children, Communism, Religion, & Facts*. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Karl-Marx>

- Kenton, W. (2024, May 7). *Karl Marx: His books, theories, and impact*. Investopedia.
<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/k/karl-marx.asp>
- Crossman, A. (2024, September 19). *A brief biography of Karl Marx*. ThoughtCo.
<https://www.thoughtco.com/karl-marx-biography-3026494>
- *The Communist Manifesto: Full Work Summary* | SparkNotes. (n.d.). SparkNotes.
<https://www.sparknotes.com/philosophy/communist/summary/>
- Engels, F. (n.d.). *The principles of communism*.
<https://www.marxists.org/archive/marx/works/1847/11/prin-com.htm>